

Capital – Budgeting decision at Sitara Showroom Sukkur

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Abstract: *It was the evening of 01st May, 2014. Inventories for the month of April had been just closed at Sitara, a multi-million-rupee superstore located Adamji Market on the bunder road Sukkur, Pakistan. Muhammad Awais Memon, executive manager of the store was busy preparing a report that was to be presented in the management meeting following day. He was worried about the figures shown in the shrinkage section of the report. He was wondering which option he should propose to the management team RFID or Rubee System, given the already high operating cost and maintenance costs. The new product security system would have to be supplemented with the RFID tags or Rubee tags attached to the products. He believed that the new equipment would immediately reduce the shrinkage costs to almost a negligible amount. After the system is in place, the only possible shrinkage costs will come from damage or fault product delivery. But it seemed to him very difficult to convince his management team especially the owner, Younis Memon, about the installation of the system since it become necessary to have a huge investment in the equipment and tags*

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Introduction to Sitara:

Younis Memon and his brothers used to manage a wholesale cloth shop named Sami center and a construction business named Marhaba Constructions since 1994 in Adamji market of Sukkur, the hub for women and men shopping along with wholesaling and retailing. He has started these businesses with the collaboration of his brothers. Having managed these two stores successfully and profitably for almost one and a half decade, Younis Memon now wanted his venture to expand. He also thought of expanding his existing business Sami center or establishing a garment factory at Karachi. At the time he realized that the market place was getting increasingly congested over the years and the self service model store are capturing the market day by day, he came up with an idea of establishing a garment showroom with a name Sitara Showroom. This business was basically initiated by the well experienced business community of Memon in Sukkur. Sitara Showroom was established in 2007 by Mr. Younis Memon as per need of the customers of Sukkur. The new store was opened in the same area two streets across Sami center. Initially the layout of the new store was greatly appreciated and attracted a great number of customers because of appealing layout, quality products and services. Mr. Younis despite of good sales was not happy so he bought some more changes through hiring an interior decorator and revising policies and quality of product and services along with providing after sales services. After revising all things he re-launched the self service based showroom in December, 2008.

Since then this store has been attracting innumerable eyes in Sukkur and has, by early October 2009 totaled a market share of roughly 14 percent of the total garment market in Sukkur. This approach of Mr. Younis was successful and turned to enormous sales. People praise it while they talk about garment shopping in their gossips. Many people perceive it to be a good place for a mere visit and window shopping. Many people also perceive it to be a place from where they can get quality product every time.

Located nearby a famous Indus river this showroom bears gravity to crowds of people from all over the city. Many people from Rohri, a sister city adjacent Sukkur, also pay visit to Sitara showroom when they come for shopping at Sukkur. The showroom is not only famous for its beauty and policies, but also popular because of its items being cost effective to the customers.

Establishment and growth:

In 2007 Sitara conducted a demographic study. He came to know that most of the people were not satisfied with their shopping pattern and they do not get quality products because they face many counterfeit products. People want a place where they can shop on their own and get only quality products every time. Mr. Younis had read about X-architects, a famous architect firm; he contacted X-architects and invited him to prepare a map for upcoming store. X-architects came all the way from Dubai, and visited the site. The architect was briefed about the vision of Mr. Younis along with the culture of Sukkur city, according to Mr. Younis the new venture is the mega source for the people of Sukkur from where they can get quality products every time. The map was prepared shortly and an attractive building was

constructed, at the site, two streets across the Sami center at Adamji market on bunder road. The venture was named as Sitara Showroom.

Currently Sitara employees over 08 people and host nearly 03 different categories of products. Sitara has been able to attract 20 percent of Sukkur's garment market. Most of the people that came to Sitara are from elite class, especially government officials who do not compromise on quality of product. According to Mr. Younis he has a substantial volume of sales and he is capturing the market very fast because of the following factors;

1- Nominal price:

As Sitara provides quality products and believe in providing superior customer satisfaction, they offer nominal prices for their quality products which are their competitive edge. They have made an image in the mind of people/customer that they will get every time quality product at nominal price from Sitara.

2- Supportive staff:

At the time you go to Sitara you will find well dressed, well mannered and courteous staff as a part of their quality products, package and service.

3- Sense of security:

Mr. Younis is well aware of the local cultural values and he have kept those values in consideration before opening this new venture, their building provide you complete security and sense of belongingness. According to one of the loyal customer of Sitara, "Regardless of my belongingness to area (rural/urban) and gender I do not feel socially insecure when I am in the store". There is a strict policy for dealing with the people who create problem or tries to become the bone of contention. However, there are no chances of discrimination between males and females; all are treated equally with equal attention.

4- Image of Sitara as a brand:

Sitara has a strong brand image, and good social spot for middle and elite class people. People perceive it as a symbol of their status and a place where they can get quality product every time.

5- Artistic architecture and efficient layout:

The architecture of Sitara is like a palace with attractive shelf's filled with products. There is a separate region for each type of product but yet all of them are of quality.

6- Strategic location:

Sitara is situated in the heart of business hub of Sukkur, near historic Indus River. A number of whole sellers and retailers are located nearby so you do not have to travel a long distance if you want to visit Sitara after you are done with your market business.

7- Unique Policy:

Mr. Younis after analyzing some market factors came up with an attractive and unique policy, that if a customer is facing after purchase conflict he/she is free to come back and return the product within 15 days, Sitara will pay them back their complete money without asking even a single question.

Problem faced by Sitara along with shopping trend of Sukkur:

Sukkur city is the third largest city of the province Sindh, it is a small city with an area of 5165 square kilometer and a population of 930,000 people.

For many people in this region of Sindh, for them it is not a big issue if they or their family member especially child hide some products in their pockets. They treat it as a fun and once the child's theft is become visible, the punishment by their parent is not very strict, which is not enough for a child to stop them from stealing the products from the store next time. Some people think that it is their rights to pocket a little, such practices are usually common in less educated people.

Sitara had already been informed about the rapid increase of shrinkage cost with the expansion of the store, but Mr. Younis was always stubborn and he ignored this with saying, "we trust our customers and it is up to them that how they maintain our trust, if they broke our trust by stealing something in real they are spoiling their image".

Sitara had previously faced one major issue in terms of billing so Mr. Younis had recently installed an electronic billing system which accepts credit cards, Visa cards and cash. On payment it generates electronic receipt which minimizes the errors and the record was kept and updated constantly.

Main problem and decision:

To maximize the security, Mr. Younis had already installed 06 security cameras within Sitara showroom. The main aim of this decision was to maximize security and to minimize the shrinkage cost, but this step was not fruitful because there is no dedicated person for watching the monitor all the time. He was now confused that it was the customers who cause the shrinkage or it was his own employees who stole, since they had an easy access to all products and places. A friend of Mr. Younis now suggested him to install RFID (Radio frequency identification) technology, but Mr. Awais Memon who was a business graduate from Sukkur IBA and working as an executive manager at the store suggested to install Rubee technology which is an alternative of RFID technology.

After analyzing both options Mr. Younis come to know that Rubee is the technology which is used to increase visibility network it have an area range of 10-50 feet, and is capable of working in harsh environment with network of many thousands of tags. The other few distinguishing factor that made Mr. Younis confused in selecting the technology are;

- RuBee is mainly a visibility tool, while RFID is used for track and trace. RuBee tags are equipped with IP (internet protocol) addresses; hence their status can be checked from the Internet.
- RFID tag is based on mainly on radio signals with a very small percentage of magnetic/inductive signals, RuBee is just the opposite. Since RuBee doesn't rely on radio signals, it is unaffected by liquids and metals, and are capable of being used underwater and underground. Their ability to function in the presence of metal makes them suitable for use on store shelves and shopping carts, which may prove ideal for item-level tagging. However this is a key restraint in case of RFID tags.
- There is no significant price difference between RuBee and RFID. While RuBee has infrastructure costs that are lower than RFID, its tag costs can be higher, depending on tag characteristics.
- There is very little overlap in applications for the two technologies. RFID would still be the technology of choice where high-volume scanning is required. RuBee, on the other hand, might prove to be the ideal solution for tagging individual items of high-end merchandise.
- In terms of read rates, RuBee can only handle about 10 reads per second. It works on long wavelength, low speed, low power and medium range. RFID, by comparison, can handle 150 to 200 reads, and is hence more appropriate when reading high volume items.
- Rubee uses less energy as compared to the RFID technology.
- Rubee has long life as compared to RFID technology.

Mr. Younis want to purchase one of the two technologies. Both technologies are not available in Pakistan and had to be imported from Dubai or China, in times of repair and maintenance, the cost would be higher. Apart from this every RFID tags would cost Rs: 15 per piece of product this will increase the cost of each product by Rs: 15, ignoring the depreciation of equipment and magnetizers and demagnetizers. The system would detect any such product which has not been demagnetized by the RFID reader, and the bell will ring when the product is being taken out of gate.

Beside this every Rubee tags would cost Rs: 30 per piece of product this will increase the cost of each product by Rs: 30, ignoring the depreciation of equipment and magnetizers and demagnetizers. The working is same as the RFID

Mr. Younis has also analyzed that if he will not take any step the shrinkage cost will increase by an estimate of 06 percent yearly. But he was also thinking that whether it would be a wise decision to install such expensive machinery as already he has invested a huge amount on electronic billing technology.

The data regarding products, sales and technology cost is given below:

Products:

For gents;

- 1- Gents Kurtas, Shilwar kammez (it is the type of current sindhi dress).
- 2- Shirt piece means high quality of shirt cloths is available (un-sewed).
- 3- High quality of dress paints for students and professional are available.
- 4- Readymade funky and qualitative jeans.
- 5- Cloths pieces for two pieces.
- 6- Variety of the coat cloth pieces is available. And other products.

Ladies items;

- 1- Special loan (type of cloth piece), Cotton, and other varieties of cloths suits.
- 2- Ladies purses bridal purse, bridal cloths available with different varieties and colors.
- 3- Hand bag, night dresses and many type of ladies garment are available.

General items;

- 1- Towels, bed sheets and blanket, Child care products, gift items perfume and body spray.

Above are major products offered by Sitara Showroom; the uniqueness of Sitara showroom is that it provide customer with greater variety and all the products comes from proper channels.

Sales:

	Seasonal	non-seasonal
Sales	Rs: 62,000,000	Rs: 26,000,000
Profit	Rs: 15,500,000	Rs: 6,500,000
Shrinkage cost	Rs: 85,000	

According to Mr. Younis Memon they earn standard 25% profit of their sales.

Total investment in business reported 400 million which include all the expenditure of acquiring land building, equipment and other expenses.

Technology cost:

RFID Technology;

Initial investment	Rs: 6,375,000	Tag cost	Rs: 15/ per tag
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Rubee Technology;

Initial investment	Rs: 4,658,000	Tag cost	Rs: 35/ per tag
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Mr. Younis want to purchase one of the technologies with debt to equity ratio 1:3 beside this they also want to purchase one stand by generator for any of the technology. On debt the interest rate is 14%.

Vision of Sitara:

“Providing rapid response to the customers as to save time and reduce employee’s idol time”.

SWOT analysis:

- 1- Strengths;
 - a. Strong brand image
 - b. Good supply chain
 - c. Loyal customers
 - d. Quality products
 - e. Fix prices
- 2- Weaknesses;
 - a. Illiterate employees
 - b. Power shortage
 - c. High shrinkage cost
- 3- Opportunities;
 - a. Also provide flexible price option
 - b. Train employee to increase their output
 - c. Use stand by generator
- 4- Threats;
 - a. New entrants
 - b. Discounts offered by local retailers
 - c. Lack of timely delivery of raw material

Analyze the entire situation and suggest Mr. Younis Memom,

- Should he go for purchasing of the new technology?
- Which technology should he purchase and why? Provide strong reasoning.